

Moderating Lightning sessions

Logistics slides with room assignments: <https://tinyurl.com/Day2Lightning>
https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/12A3G1M840yhY6HbQgWj9_7-EiSmV_etFdAsj-UB4PUs/edit?usp=sharing

- **Before doing anything else, start the recording.**
- Ask who in the room is the notetaker. If no one responds, ask for a volunteer.
- First, guide them from the agenda to the correct google doc for the session. If in-person, direct them to the workshop poster for the QR code. Place this link in the Webex chat.

Wednesday, May 8, 2024		
Time (ET)	Agenda Item	Presenter/Notes
Day 2: Community Software Efforts at NASA - Opportunities and Challenges		Day 2 Google Folder Morning Moderator: Demitri Muna Afternoon Moderator: Brian Thomas
9:30 am - 9:50 am	Invited Talk on Community Software Efforts at NASA	Julie Barnum
9:50 am - 10:30 am	Software at NASA: Highlighted Talks with Q&A	Ross Beyer Luis Lopez David Aronchick Ziheng Sun
10:30 am - 10:35 am	Logistics of Breakouts	Rebecca Ringuette
10:35 am - 11:20 am	Software at NASA: Lightning Breakout 1	(See Lightning Folder)
11:20 am - 11:35 am	Break (15 minutes)	
11:35 am - 12:20 pm	Software at NASA: Lightning Breakout 2	

Shared with me > 2024 NASA Software W... > Day 2 > Lightning Breakouts ▾

1 selected

Name	Last modified	File size
Lightning Breakout Ro...	7:06 PM me	5 KB
Lightning Presentation	...	2 KB
Lightning Presentation	...	3 KB
Lightning Presentation	...	3 KB
Lightning Presentation	Apr 26, 2024 me	3 KB
Lightning Presentations 1E: Notes	Apr 26, 2024 me	3 KB

Context menu options: Open with, Download, Rename, Make a copy, Share, Organize, File information, Make available offline, Move to trash.

Share sub-menu options: Share, Copy link, Approvals.

- Also show them how to access the slides for that session (will be view only).
- Direct all attendees to sign in to the google notes doc for the session.
- Communicate that each presenter has 3 minutes per presentation, which includes time for questions. When the 3 minute timer sounds, the next person will begin talking.
- Direct attendees to submit questions through the Q&A feature. (If none is available, ask them to put their questions in the chat with @name for the name of the relevant presenter.)
- When the presentations are over, further questions will be asked from the Q&A/chat as time allows.
- Direct those interested in deeper discussion with a given presenter to consult the relevant slide for their contact information.
- Set a three minute timer on your phone or other device to signal the next person to begin talking. **Enforce this time limit strictly.** Please attempt to give a 30 second or 1 minute warning to the presenter and indicate you will do this before the presentations begin.
- **Make sure to end on time.**
- Note: If a presenter requests to be shifted to later in the same session, please try your best to accommodate that request. Shifts to later sessions are not always possible, but you should **ask Rebecca Ringuette** about this.